

Synthesis of tert-butyl-substituted 3-carboxy coumarins in water in the presence of para toluene sulfonic acid (PTSA) as a catalyst

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3-Carboxycoumarins are important initial compounds for the synthesis of coumarins. Coumarins are natural products and well known for their diverse biological activities. Substituted coumarin-3-carboxylic acid derivatives were potent and selective inhibitors of monoamine oxidases [1].

PTSA (para toluene sulfonic acid) has been used as a catalyst in the synthesis of tert-butyl-substituted 3-carboxy coumarins [2].

Here we describe a two-component condensation reaction between antert-butylsalicylaldehydes and Meldrum acid efficiently provides tert-butyl-substituted 3-carboxy coumarins in a one-pot reaction in the presence of PTSA as catalyst (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

References:

1. R.D.H. Murray, J. Mendez, S.A. Brown, *The Natural Coumarin: Occurrence. Chemistry and Biochemistry*; John Wiley & Sons: New York, (1982).
2. D.Q. Shi, H. Yao, *J. Heterocycl. chem.* 46 (2009) 1335.